

COMPARISON OF SATISFACTION OF DISTANCE LEARNERS IN AN UNDERGRADUATE PROGRAMME OF INDIRA GANDHI NATIONAL OPEN UNIVERSITY (IGNOU) AMONG REGIONS OF JAMMU AND DELHI

¹ROHINI SHARMA BHARDWAJ

¹ASSISTANT PROFESSOR

¹SCHOOL OF HEALTH SCIENCES,

¹IGNOU, DELHI, INDIA

Abstract : Student satisfaction is an important indicator of the quality of learning in distance education. This paper explores the quality of support received by distance learners enrolled in Undergraduate Bachelor of Arts programme of IGNOU at two study centers located at Jammu and Delhi with a view to evaluate the level of satisfaction of the distance learners by survey research approach. The paper compares the satisfaction of the distance learners in these regions which are different in terms of location, infrastructure and expertise of counselors. The findings of the study reflect that irrespective of these differences, the learner satisfaction is similar and learners by and large are satisfied with the services. Thus, we can conclude that IGNOU is successful in reaching out to its learners irrespective of various limitations which speaks volumes about the effectiveness of its student support.

IndexTerms - IGNOU: Indira Gandhi National Open University, Distance Learning, Student Satisfaction, Regional Center (RC)

1. INTRODUCTION

Distance learning is extremely flexible and does not require monotonous class room for teaching - learning to take place and can be virtually delivered anywhere. Especially useful for adults and those who have demanding professional commitments and family responsibilities.

It is worthwhile to investigate student satisfaction in distance education especially in the light of new technology. The quality of interaction, use of information and communication technology (ICT) are the various factors which need to be investigated when looking up for the student satisfaction in distance learning . Much of the recent literature reveals that perceptions of distance education range from “extremely beneficial” to the more negative view of the phenomenon as a “false gold rush” . Hence, it is important to study the student satisfaction of distance learners in order to find out the loop holes and improve upon the distance education reach out to its learners .

Since, IGNOU is one of the largest university in Asia in distance education , hence, it is important to understand how much the learners are satisfied from the university’s student support and if there is any differences in the satisfactions of students in two different regions – one a metropolitan city and capital of the Country –Delhi and another city with a rural backdrop-Jammu.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

To compare the Satisfaction of Distance Learners in an Undergraduate Programme of Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU) among Regions of Jammu and Delhi.

3. OBJECTIVES

1. To study the satisfaction of distance learners of Jammu and Delhi region regarding Self learning material provided by IGNOU.
2. To study the satisfaction of distance learners of Jammu and Delhi region regarding support services provided by IGNOU.
3. To compare the findings of learners of Jammu and Delhi region of IGNOU.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Research approach : “Survey approach” with “comparative research design” aimed to study the satisfaction of distance learners.

4.2 Variables under study

Independent variables: Satisfaction of distance learners in regions of Jammu and Delhi of IGNOU.

Dependent variables: Self Learning material and Support Services provided by IGNOU.

4.3 Setting of the study : Selected Programme Study Centres of IGNOU in region of Jammu and Delhi. The Programme study centre at Jammu was GOVT. M.A.M. COLLEGE, University of Jammu, Jammu, J and K -180004 (Code-1232). The Programme study centre at Delhi for the study was Acharya Institute of Professional Studies,2647, Hudson Lane, North Campus New Delhi-110009 (Code-0772).

4.4 Population : Distance learners enrolled in Undergraduate programme of IGNOU under Regional center (RC) Jammu and Regional center (RC) Delhi-2.

4.5 Sample and sample size : The sample comprised of distance learners enrolled in Bachelor of Arts programme of IGNOU under RC Jammu and RC Delhi-2. Sample size for this study was 60. 30 distance learners under RC Jammu and 30 distance learners under RC Delhi-2. Sample was selected by total enumeration sampling technique.

4.6 Data collection tool and technique

A Likert-type scale as described below was used a data collection tool. The tool consisted of:

PART A with 5 items on personal data, such as gender, age group, marital status, economic status and area.

PART B: It comprised of total 24 items to illicit data on satisfaction of the distance learners. Out of this 3 items were on Self learning material and rest was on support services.

Thus, a total of 32 items were included in the rating scale .The learners were required to express their satisfaction .There were 5 points used as ‘strongly agree’(SA=5), ‘moderately agree’(MA=4), ‘undecided/neither agree nor disagree’(UD=3), ‘moderately disagree’(MD=2) and ‘strongly disagree’(SD=1). The learners had to indicate degree of agreement or disagreement by checking one of five response categories in each item mentioned in Part B. Content validity was established and Reliability was computed to be 0.87. 6.

4.7 Data collection procedure :

The data collection in Jammu region was done at Govt. M.A.M. COLLEGE, University of Jammu, Jammu, J and K - 180004 (Code-1232). The data was collected from Acharya Institute of Professional Studies,2647, Hudson Lane, North Campus New Delhi-110009 (Code-0772) for Delhi region. The time period was April –May 2016.

The data was collected by giving taking formal administrative approval . Self introduction and establishment of rapport with the academic counselor and distance learners. The ethical clearance was taken from the institution and consent was also taken. The learners were told to give a free and frank response. They were also assured confidentiality of their responses.

5. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA**5.1 Description of sample characteristics :**

Frequency and percentage distribution of distance learners in terms of gender, age group, marital status, economic status and area in regions of Jammu and Delhi have been given in the Table 1.

Table 1: Sample Characteristics of Distance learners in Jammu and Delhi regions of IGNOU

S. No.	Variables	Distance learners of Jammu Region of IGNOU (N=30)		Distance learners of Delhi Region of IGNOU (N=30)		Distance learners of Jammu and Delhi Region of IGNOU (N=60)	
		Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
1.	Gender: a. Male	17	57%	20	67%	37	61%
	b. Female	13	43%	10	33%	23	39%
2.	Age Group: a. 18-30	30	100%	29	96%	59	96%
	b. 31-45	-	-	1	4%	1	4%
	c.45 and Above	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	Marital Status: a. Married	1	4%	2	6%	3	5%
	b. Unmarried	29	96%	28	94%	57	95%
4.	Economic Status: a. Employed	-	-	2	6%	2	3%
	b. Unemployed	30	100%	27	90%	57	95%
	c. No response	-	-	1	4%	1	2%
5.	Area: a. Urban	11	37%	27	90%	38	64%
	b. Rural	17	57%	3	10%	20	33%
	c. No response	2	6%	-	-	2	3%

5.2 Satisfaction of Distance learners of Jammu and Delhi regions on self - learning material provided by IGNOU

Findings on 3 items included:

1. Many (53%) distance learners from Jammu Region “strongly agreed” that they received the learning materials on time. 50 % from Delhi region “moderately agreed” to this.
2. 44% distance learners from Jammu Region “strongly agreed” and 53%, distance learners from Delhi region “moderately agreed” that printed material was helpful in self-learning.
3. 41% distance learners from Jammu Region and 73%, distance learners from Delhi region (n=30) “moderately agreed” to being satisfied with information in programme guide.

Mean, median and standard deviation of scores regarding satisfaction of distance learners on Self Learning Material provided by IGNOU is given in Table2.

Table 2: Mean, median and standard deviation of satisfaction scores of distance learners on Self Learning Material provided by IGNOU

Area	Region	Maximum score	Range of Scores	Mean	Median	Mode	S.D.
Satisfaction scores on Self Learning Material	Jammu Region of IGNOU (n=30)	15	8-15	12	12	13	4.24
	Delhi Region of IGNOU (n=30)	15	6-15	11	12	12	7.34
	Jammu and Delhi Region of IGNOU (N=60)	15	6-15	12	12	12	8.1

The data presented in the Table-2 shows, that the mean satisfaction score on Self learning material was= 12, median = 12, Mode 13 and standard deviation was 4.24 for Jammu region .and mean satisfaction score on Self learning material was = 11, median = 12, Mode 12 and standard deviation was 7.34 for Delhi regions. Moreover, mean, mode and median show that the two groups are comparable. The mean, median and mode for both regions taken together is 12 with standard deviation of 8.1. The obtained scores ranged from 6-15.

Frequency polygon of the scores plotted as in Figure 1 shows that the distribution of scores of distance learners ranged from 6-15 for N=60, with a maximum frequency of 29 for the score of 12. This implies that distance learners are “moderately satisfied” with the “self instructional material” of IGNOU.

Fig 1 : Frequency polygon of the satisfaction scores on “self instructional material”

5.3 Satisfaction of distance learners of Jammu and Delhi regions on support services provided by IGNOU

Findings included:

1. Most of the distance learners of Jammu Region “strongly agreed” and many distance learners from Delhi region “moderately agreed” to be satisfied with 7 items pertaining to pre-admission and during admission counseling, academic counselors helping over the telephone, website of the university, audio-video materials, availability of books at regional/study centers, examination system and support services provided by IGNOU
2. For the rest of the items, many distance learners from Jammu Region and Delhi region “moderately agreed” to being satisfied with 17 items pertaining to :
 - attending induction programme
 - receiving the counseling schedule in time
 - academic counselors clarified difficult concepts/ doubts
 - techniques used in counseling sessions
 - academic counselors were cordial and cooperative
 - Academic counselors helped to develop and improve study skills
 - satisfied with guidance and support for practical's
 - satisfied receiving guidance for project work
 - academic counseling sessions helped to prepare them for the term-end examination
 - number of academic counseling sessions
 - satisfied with counseling at study centers
 - receiving evaluated assignments in time
 - comments of the evaluators
 - grades received in assignments
 - laboratory facilities at study centers
 - services of the support staff at study centers
 - duration of publication of results

Mean, median and standard deviation of scores regarding satisfaction of distance learners on Support Services by IGNOU is given in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean, median and standard deviation of satisfaction scores of distance learners on Support Services provided by IGNOU

Area	Region	Maximum score	Range of Scores	Mean	Median	Mode	S.D
Satisfaction Scores on Support Services	Jammu Region of IGNOU (n=30)	120	60-105	88	91.5	95	20.1
	Delhi Region of IGNOU (n=30)	120	66-111	90	91.5	95	22.2
	Jammu and Delhi Region of IGNOU (N=60)	120	60-111	88	91	95	55

The data presented in the Table-5 shows, that the mean score about support services was = 88, median = 91.5, Mode 95 and standard deviation was 20.1 for Jammu region and mean satisfaction score = 90, median = 91.5, Mode 95 and standard deviation was 22.2 for Delhi region of IGNOU. This shows that the two groups are comparable. Moreover, mean, mode and median for Jammu and Delhi regions together was 88, 91 and 95, respectively with standard deviation of 55. The obtained scores ranged from 60-111.

Frequency polygon of the scores plotted as in Figure 2 showed that the distribution of satisfaction scores of distance learners ranged from 60-111 for N=60, with a maximum frequency of 27 for the scores between 90-99. This suggests that many of the distance learners were “moderately satisfied” with the “self instructional material” of IGNOU.

5.4 Comparison of satisfaction of distance learners of Jammu and Delhi regions of IGNOU The comparison of scores was done by using Mann –Whitney U test which is the non-parametric analogue of Independent “t” test.

i) Comparison of Satisfaction of distance learners of Jammu and Delhi regions of IGNOU on self- learning material:

The scores related to satisfaction regarding Self Instructional Material were ranked and “U” value calculated is represented in Table 4.

Fig 2 : Frequency polygon of the satisfaction scores on "support services"

Table 4: "U" value for Jammu and Delhi regions on Self learning Material provided by IGNOU

Region	Sum of ranks	Mean of ranks	"U" value	Z- value	p-value
Jammu Region of IGNOU (n=30)	919	30.63	446 ^{NS}	0.0517 ^{NS}	0.96012 ^{NS}
Delhi Region of IGNOU (n=30)	911	30.37			

NS at $p \leq 0.05$

The "U" value thus, obtained is 446 which is not significant at 0.05 levels of significance. The Z-Score is 0.0517. The p-value is 0.96012. The result is not significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

This implies that there was no difference in the satisfaction of distance learners of Jammu and Delhi region related to on Self learning Material provided by IGNOU.

ii) Comparison of satisfaction of distance learners of Jammu and Delhi regions of IGNOU on support services:

The scores related to satisfaction regarding Support Services was ranked and "U" value was calculated is represented in Table 5.

Table 5: "U" value for Jammu and Delhi regions on Self learning Material provided by IGNOU

Region	Sum of ranks	Mean of ranks	"U" value	Z- value	p-value
Jammu Region of IGNOU (n=30)	869.5	28.98	404.5 ^{NS}	0.6653 ^{NS}	0.50286 ^{NS}
Delhi Region of IGNOU (n=30)	960.5	32.02			

NS at $p \leq 0.05$

The "U" value thus, obtained is 404.5 which is not significant at 0.05 levels of significance. The Z-Score is 0.6653. The p-value is 0.50286. The result is not significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

This implies that there was no difference in the satisfaction of distance learners of Jammu and Delhi region related to Support Services provided by IGNOU.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be derived:

1. Distance Learners were satisfied with the self instructional material and support services provided by IGNOU in Jammu and Delhi regions.
2. There was no difference in satisfaction of distance learners regarding self instructional material and support services provided by IGNOU in Jammu and Delhi region.

The findings reveal that quality of distance education provided by IGNOU is one of the best. IGNOU uses decentralized approach to reach out to its learners with an effective system of support services despite various limitations.

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